

DExplore - Differential Gene Expression Analysis

DExplore- User's guide

1. Introduction

DExplore is an online and user-friendly tool designed for detecting differentially expressed (DE) genes using data sourced from the international public repository NCBI GEO. In addition to identifying DE genes, DExplore also provides interactive graphical representations, including heatmaps and volcano plots. This feature enables users to easily visualize the data. Complementing histograms, boxplots, and PCA plots are also provided. Furthermore, DExplore offers the capability to perform functional enrichment analysis using a built-in version of the well-established web tool WebGestalt¹ (www.webgestalt.org).

Users can also upload data that have not been submitted to GEO yet. These user-uploaded data are only temporarily saved on the server and are automatically deleted as soon as the user exits the platform, or their session expires. This ensures that there is no danger of the data being copied or used by anyone other than the user.

DExplore is built utilizing the R programming language and Bioconductor and can be easily used by researchers with no specialized programming skills require.

The user interface is quite simple, and the application runs exclusively online, so users do not have to download or store raw data in their computer.

In addition, both the source code and the docker image can be accessed and downloaded using the links on the homepage.

Currently, DExplore can only be used to analyze single-channel mRNA microarray experiments for Affymetrix[®] platforms but will be expanded soon to be used for other commercially available platforms such as Illumina and Agilent.

2. How to use

DExplore is comprised of four tab panels; Data Input, Data Description, Results and WebGestalt Over-Representation Analysis.

Do not forget to refresh DExplore between analyses.

Analyses differ depending on the type of data the user wants to use.

a. Using DExplore with NCBI GEO's microarray data

The first thing users must do is to enter a valid GSE accession number from the NCBI GEO Database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>) and press the button "Submit" in the "Data Input" tab.

Important notice: enter only the number without writing "GSE" (e.g., for Series "GSE41827", enter "41827").

After a few minutes (time depends on the submitted data size), DExplore provides a hyperlink to the GEO's corresponding page.

In the Data Description tab, users must choose the parameters for analysis, including the platform to be used (important for experiments utilizing microarray chips from multiple platforms), the comparison criterion, and which samples are to be treated as controls and compared to. After selecting each parameter, users should press the submit button to proceed.

Subsequently, the user must select certain statistical parameters required for the analysis, including the method for adjusting the p-value for multiple comparisons, the absolute \log_2 Fold Change threshold, and the adjusted p-value threshold (see Appendix below). Users have the option to either use the default parameters, which include False Discovery Rate (FDR) for multiple comparisons adjustment, 0.5 as the absolute \log_2 Fold Change threshold, and 0.05 as the adjusted p-value threshold, or customize these values as needed. After selecting the desired parameters, the user must press the "Run the analysis" button and wait a few minutes for the analysis to be completed.

Select the adjustment method

holm
 hochberg
 hommel
 bonferroni
 BH
 BY
 fdr
 none

Set the absolute logFC threshold:

0.001 0.5 2

0.001 0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1 1.2 1.4 1.6 1.8 2

Set the adjusted P value:

0.05 0.5

0.001 0.051 0.101 0.151 0.201 0.251 0.301 0.351 0.401 0.451 0.5

press Run the analysis

Run the analysis

b. Using DExplore with your own .CEL files

If the user wishes to use data that have not been submitted to the NCBI GEO, they can utilize the right side of the tab panel to browse their computer and select the files for analysis. The user should ensure that raw data is stored in .CEL format, with one file per experimental condition and replicate. After selecting the files and pressing the "Submit" button, DExplore provides a table showing information about the experimental design in the "Data Description" tab.

Important notice: When using uploaded data for analysis, users are encouraged to upload treated samples before control ones. This can be achieved by renaming the .CEL files accordingly, ensuring that treated samples precede control samples in the file list. Maintaining this order is crucial for accurately identifying DEGs, as DExplore analyzes data based on the order of samples provided. By prioritizing treated samples, DExplore can precisely identify upregulated and downregulated genes in accordance with the experimental design and treatment conditions.

Upload your own .CEL files *

Browse... 6 files

Upload complete

Submit

* This field is mandatory

The user is required to fill in the table providing information about the experimental design, including specifying which samples consist the control data and identifying the treatment for treated samples. For treated samples, users must specify the type of treatment, duration, and concentration for chemical substances or dose for radiation, if applicable.

However, if duration and concentration do not affect the experimental design, users may leave these columns blank. Regardless, the columns for "treatment" and "replicate" must be filled out. After completing the table, users should press the "Save changes" button.

DExplore - Differential Gene Expression Analysis Data Input Data Description Results WebGestalt Over-Representation Analysis About

Column visibility Search:

sample	treatment	duration	concentration	replicate
GSM1025049_Cas_Control1_HG-U133_Plus_2_CEL	control	duration	concentration	1
GSM1025050_Cas_Control2_HG-U133_Plus_2_CEL	control	duration	concentration	2
GSM1025051_Cas_Control3_HG-U133_Plus_2_CEL	control	duration	concentration	3
GSM1025052_Cas_II-gly1_HG-U133_Plus_2_CEL	Cas_II-gly	duration	concentration	1
GSM1025053_Cas_II-gly2_HG-U133_Plus_2_CEL	Cas_II-gly	duration	concentration	2
GSM1025054_Cas_II-gly3_HG-U133_Plus_2_CEL	Cas_II-gly	duration	concentration	3

Showing 1 to 6 of 6 entries Previous Next

Please, use valid names for treatment. A syntactically valid name consists of letters, numbers, the dot or underscore characters, and starts with a letter or the dot not followed by a number. Spaces are not allowed.

Columns 'treatment' and 'replicate' should be filled out!

Double click to complete the table and then press Save changes

Save changes

After saving the changes, the user must choose which of the possible comparisons will be carried out. For example, in cases involving two different treatment methods, A and B, along with control samples, the user may choose to (1) compare A to control, (2) compare B to control, or (3) compare A to B.

Select the comparison

control-- vs. Cas_II-gly--

Submit

In the next step, users must select certain statistical parameters required for the analysis, including the method for adjusting the p-value for multiple comparisons, the absolute \log_2 Fold Change threshold, and the adjusted p-value threshold (see Appendix below). Users have the option to either use the default parameters, which include False Discovery Rate (FDR) for multiple comparisons adjustment, 0.5 as the absolute \log_2 Fold Change threshold, and 0.05 as the adjusted p-value threshold, or customize these values as needed. Once the parameters are set, users must press the 'Run the analysis' button and wait a few minutes for the analysis to be completed.

Select the adjustment method

- holm
- hochberg
- hommel
- bonferroni
- BH
- BY
- fdr
- none

Set the absolute logFC threshold:

0.001 0.5 2

0.001 0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1 1.2 1.4 1.6 1.8 2

Set the adjusted P value:

0.05 0.5

0.001 0.051 0.101 0.151 0.201 0.251 0.301 0.351 0.401 0.451 0.5

press Run the analysis

Run the analysis

3. Results

When the analysis is completed, in the “Results” tab the user can view a list of the differentially expressed genes (both the probe ID used by Affymetrix® and the gene symbol are provided) and some statistical values for each of them. In the gene symbol column, there is also a hyperlink to NCBI’s Gene database, in case the user wishes to explore the genes on the list.

The screenshot shows the 'Results' tab of the DExplore application. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Results' selected. Below the navigation bar, a text box explains that results can be downloaded as visualization plots, a .csv file, or a .tsv file. Below this text are three buttons: 'Visualization plots', '.csv file', and '.tsv file'. Below the buttons is a table with columns: probeID, gene symbol, logFC, AveExpr, t, PValue, adj.PVal, and B. The table contains five rows of data. Below the table are buttons for 'Column visibility', 'Copy', and 'Print', and a search box.

probeID	gene symbol	logFC	AveExpr	t	PValue	adj.PVal	B
117_at	HSPA6	7.51	9.93	121	1.18e-14	1.77e-10	22.5
200664_s_at	DNAJB1	2.46	11.7	74.2	6.41e-13	1.90e-9	20.0
203665_at	HMOX1	4.38	10.8	67.7	1.35e-12	2.90e-9	19.4
207574_s_at	GADD45B	3.37	10.3	63.0	2.45e-12	4.07e-9	18.9
202431_s_at	MYC	-3.61	9.14	-60.5	3.43e-12	4.73e-9	18.6

There is also the option to print the list (in order to save as a .pdf file), copy it to clipboard and then paste it in another file, or download the list as a .csv or a .tsv file in order to use it for further analyses.

Furthermore, users can easily download a zip file containing graphical representations of the Differential Expression Analysis by clicking the corresponding button.

4. WebGestalt Over-Representation Analysis

After detecting differentially expressed genes under two experimental conditions, it is common practice to proceed to functional enrichment analysis. DExplore facilitates this process by enabling users to perform functional enrichment analysis using the well-established web tool WebGestalt (www.webgestalt.org). By clicking the 'WebGestalt ORA' button, users are prompted to select one of the supported organisms from the WebGestalt platform and one of the reference sets to which the list of differentially expressed genes will be compared.

The screenshot shows the 'WebGestalt Over-Representation Analysis' section of the DExplore web application. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the following tabs: 'DExplore - Differential Gene Expression Analysis', 'Data Input', 'Data Description', 'Results', 'WebGestalt Over-Representation Analysis', and 'About'. Below the navigation bar, there is a prominent 'WebGestalt ORA' button. The main content area is divided into two sections. The first section is titled 'Choose the organism for the analysis' and contains a dropdown menu with 'hsapiens' selected and a 'Submit' button. The second section is titled 'Choose the reference set for the analysis' and contains a dropdown menu with 'affy_hg_u133_plus_2' selected and another 'Submit' button.

After a few minutes, DExplore renders the results of Over-Representation Analysis, which can be explored through a browser or downloaded to the user's computer for future use.

For more information regarding the WebGestalt web tool as well as the methods used for over-representation functional enrichment analysis, please visit www.webgestalt.org.

5. Appendix

p-value and Multiple Comparisons

A p-value provides information about whether a statistical hypothesis test is significant or not and it also provides some indication on "how significant" the result is: the smaller the p-value the stronger the evidence against the null hypothesis. Most importantly, it does this without committing to a particular level of significance as traditional hypothesis tests and confidence intervals do².

In statistics, the multiple comparisons, multiplicity or multiple testing problem occurs when one considers a set of statistical inferences simultaneously or infers a subset of parameters selected based on the values observed. The more inferences are made the more likely erroneous inferences are to occur. Several statistical techniques have been developed to prevent this from happening, allowing significance levels for single and multiple comparisons to be directly compared. These techniques generally require a stricter significance threshold for individual comparisons, so as to compensate for the number of inferences being made.

Adjustment for Multiple Comparisons

A typical microarray study generates a gene expression matrix with tens of thousands of rows—probe sets representing genes. Assuming we are performing 10,000 univariate tests on 10,000 genes with a significance level (α) of 0.05, we allow a 5% chance of making a Type I error, also known as a 'false positive' finding. This means that we expect 5% of the 10,000 genes, or 500 genes, to be deemed significant (differentially expressed) by chance alone. To control the overall probability of a Type I error, we must apply a correction for multiple testing. Whether we are repeatedly performing a t test, an ANOVA F test, or any other (univariate or multivariate) test resulting in a p-value, we must adjust the individual raw p-values for multiplicity in order to control the overall posterior false positive rate.

When performing multiple tests, rather than considering the significance level of individual tests, we should use a procedure that controls one of the Type I error rates defined for testing multiple null hypotheses. Among the commonly used Type I error rates are the family-wise error rate (FWER) and the false discovery rate (FDR).

Family-wise error rate (FWER)

The family-wise error rate is defined as the probability of at least one Type I error (i.e., at least one false positive) over all tests. This probability for a single test is equal to the significance level α of the test. However, if we perform M independent tests, this probability is equal to $1 - (1 - \alpha)^M$, which for a high M is close to 1.

False discovery rate (FDR)

The false discovery rate is the expected proportion of false positives among the rejected null hypotheses (i.e., among all genes reported as differentially expressed). When all null hypotheses are true (i.e., none of the tested genes is differentially expressed), FDR is equal to FWER, but otherwise it is smaller.

Generally, procedures controlling the FWER are more conservative than those controlling FDR³. The best known among the FWER-controlling procedures are the classical single-step Bonferroni adjustment, the single-step Sidak procedure, and the step-down Holm procedure. The most popular among the FDR-controlling procedures is the step-up Benjamini and Hochberg procedure. The single-step procedures apply the same multiplicity adjustment to each individual α or raw p-value, whereas adjustments made by the stepwise approaches depend on the rank of the gene among all tested genes and on the outcomes of the tests for other genes.⁴

Adjustment Methods provided by DExplore

DExplore allows you to select an adjustment method for your analysis among the Bonferroni correction ("bonferroni"), the correction introduced by Holm (1979)⁵ ("holm"), by Hochberg (1988)⁶ ("hochberg"), by Hommel (1988)⁷ ("hommel"), by Benjamini & Hochberg (1995)⁸ ("BH" or its alias "fdr"), and by Benjamini & Yekutieli (2001)⁹ ("BY"). A pass-through option ("none") is also included.

The first four methods are designed to provide strong control of the family-wise error rate. There seems to be no reason to use the unmodified Bonferroni correction, since it is overridden by Holm's method, which is also valid under arbitrary assumptions.

Hochberg's and Hommel's methods are valid when the hypothesis tests are independent or when they are non-negatively associated.^{10,11} Hommel's method is more powerful than Hochberg's, but the difference is usually small and the Hochberg p-values are faster to compute.

The "BH" (aka "fdr") and "BY" method of Benjamini, Hochberg, and Yekutieli control the false discovery rate, the expected proportion of false discoveries amongst the rejected hypotheses. The false discovery rate is a less stringent condition than the family-wise error rate, and thus these methods are more powerful than the rest.

For a more detailed review of adjustment methods commonly used, see Shaffer, J. P. Multiple Hypothesis Testing. *Annu. Rev. Psychol.* (1995). doi:10.1146/annurev.ps.46.020195.003021.

6. References

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